

Project information	
Project acronym	Semantic x-Lab
Project full title	Semantic Search on Ontology-based Descriptions of Laboratory Workflows, Resources and Data in Helmholtz
Project start date	04/2025

Deliverable information	
Deliverable number	D1.1
Deliverable title	Define use-cases of the partner laboratories and facilities; Graph and ontology selection and technical concept using use-cases: partner laboratories and facilities
Work Package number	WP1
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Due date	08/2025
Submission date	05/2026
Comments	

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Executive summary

Deliverable D1.1 involves the evaluation and selection of ontologies that will form the basis for further work within the project. The aim was to identify and describe use cases together with our partner laboratories and facilities. A comparison of the use cases from HZDR and GFZ showed that it is possible to describe processes from different laboratory environments using the same concepts and relations. This analysis was supported by the results of our kick-off meeting with colleagues from the partner laboratories and guests from the Helmholtz Association and the NFDI environment.

To describe the concepts and relations we identified for our use case partners, we applied general scientific ontologies and domain-specific ontologies that are interoperable. Finally, these findings were used to model a first knowledge graph for the use cases using Protégé and Web Protégé.

1. Introduction

The aim of deliverable D1.1 is to identify and describe use cases together with our partner laboratories and facilities and bring them into a standardised schema in order to identify joint entities/concepts and relations. The semantic description of laboratory processes, information and data forms the basis for the knowledge graph that will be created during the Semantic x-Lab project. This includes in detail concepts and relations for e.g., lab processes, persons, organisations, instruments, methods, samples or data.

We have identified three use cases at HZDR and GFZ which are described in chapter 2 to 4. Based on these descriptions and comprehensive discussions with our colleagues from the partner laboratories and facilities, we have visualised the typical workflows in chapter 5 for each use case. The schematic illustrations of the use cases help to identify similarities and commonalities. In the next step, the concepts and relations identified from the use cases are mapped onto established ontologies, namely Metadata4Ing, OBO ontologies, HDO ontology and NFDIcore ontology.

The goal is to identify an ontology that contains classes and relations that can be used to describe the processes in the laboratories and facilities semantically and consistently in sufficient detail. This ontology is supposed to include the initial terminology to start modelling the knowledge graph, to which further external sources can be integrated at a later stage of the project.

2. Use Case I: Laser Plasma Acceleration (HZDR)

Draco is a high-power ultra-short pulse laser system for the investigation of relativistic laser plasma physics at HZDR. Experiments at this facility typically involve a target, such as a metal foil, being placed inside one of the target areas of the laser. During the laser shot, the target is destroyed and a plasma is created and measured.

The experiment starts with a planning phase during which the initial project metadata (personnel, project description, literature, laser and target parameter ranges, diagnostics) are created. During the experiment preparation phase, targets are characterised and the experimental setup (spatial arrangement, timings, measurement setup) is designed. The experimental phase consists of a cycle in which parameters are selected, a laser shot is performed, and measurements are being conducted. Based on the outcome of the

shot (live analysis of beam and particle diagnostics, image data), parameters are adjusted and the experiment cycle starts over. After the measurement campaign, data is analysed using custom software to extract experimental findings about particle acceleration and plasma. These findings are compared with previous results and simulation results, and interpreted. The experiment is finalised with publication of data, software and paper.

A typical experiment uses a variety of IT services for the purposes of data management. Experiments are documented in an electronic lab notebook which also functions as a database to track all samples as well as instruments and measurement devices. Other software solutions are in place to track parameters and diagnostics during the experiment. They are connected to the laser control software to varying degrees.

3. Use Case II: Mg isotope analysis of a soil sample (GFZ)

The use case described here refers to the procedures for sample preparation and measurement of magnesium isotopes in a soil sample in the laboratory. The sample is fictitious, but the procedures for determining element concentrations and isotope ratios in the HELGES laboratories (Helmholtz Laboratory for the Geochemistry of the Earth's Surface) at the GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences are realistic. The HELGES laboratories perform sample preparation and measurements of cosmogenic nuclides (^{10}Be , ^{26}Al) and stable isotopes of metals and metalloids (including Li, Mg, Si, Fe, Sr, B) in geological and environmental sample materials such as sediments, rocks, river water, soils, and vegetation [1].

The soil analysis experiment is divided into six phases, starting with the planning phase and ending with the publication: The planning phase includes the preparation of the field experiment. The metadata recorded so far include the organizations and persons involved, the project title and description, and the pre-registration of IGSN (*International Generic Sample Number*) [2]. After the sample material (soil) has been collected during the field experiment, a defined amount of the soil to be examined is extracted in the sampling phase using a pipette, a centrifuge, an ultrasonic bath, and various chemicals in different concentrations according to a defined method. In the next step, the sample preparation, the sample undergoes several solution steps. The sample is repeatedly evaporated and acid is added again. The individual chemical elements are separated from each other via column chromatography. In the next step, the concentration of magnesium (and the remaining matrix elements) is determined in the sample purified in this way before and after column chromatography. First, the concentration is determined using a quadrupole mass spectrometer with inductively coupled plasma. For this purpose, the liquid sample is introduced as an aerosol into the inductively coupled plasma (ICP) and the elements are ionized there. After transfer to the vacuum, the different isotopes of an element are separated in the quadrupole mass analyser and detected with a secondary electron multiplier (SEM). The detection limits are generally in the ppt to ppb range for solutions. Based on these results, the sample is prepared for measurement of the isotope ratio of magnesium using a Thermo Scientific Neptune multicollector inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (MC-ICP-MS). The sample is again introduced into the plasma as an aerosol, where the elements are ionized. The high-precision detectors enable the magnesium isotope ratio to be determined.

The data obtained in this way are evaluated and interpreted in the next step and then published, for example, in GFZ Data Services.

4. Use Case III: Nano Contact Platform (HZDR)

The clean room at HZDR focusses on research about fabrication of nanostructures and their properties, including electric, mechanical, optical and magnetic properties. For this, the exact fabrication procedures (method) are of high interest. In particular, the fabrication of nano contact platforms (NCPs) has been selected as a use case. The nano contact platform is a device designed to enable easy electrical connectivity of small structures with hard to control absolute position, like DNA based structures.

For the use case, a concrete execution of an early successful fabrication was picked. In the HZDR clean room fabrication starts by proposing a fabrication workflow which is then approved. The example execution was performed on two n-type silicon wafers. It comprises two main lithography sections, which can be distinguished by the type of photoresist used (positive/negative). In the first section, an oxide layer is formed and patterned using positive photoresist and the pattern is transferred by oxide etching. In the second section, a negative photoresist and a second lithography mask are used to define deposited structures, which are formed by metal deposition and lift-off. The process is completed by dicing and packaging after inspection. During the process, the person and date as well as specific other parameters are recorded for each step. The selected concrete fabrication execution deviated slightly from the planned process because an extra cleaning step was added in the beginning and soft contact was chosen instead of the planned hard contact, for the exposure of the second lithography section.

The data collected during the process are mainly used to control and improve the fabrication process and to monitor the state of the laboratory equipment. They are subsequently retained as provenance. The main outcome of the process are the nano contact platforms which can form the starting point for future experiments.

5. Schematic illustration of the use cases

The following pages show the schematic illustrations of the use cases. Figure 1 displays the legend for the concepts identified in the workflow of the use cases. The concepts are represented by individual colours.

Legend:

Figure 1: Legend of the laboratory workflows. The individual concepts are colour-coded.

Figure 2: Schematic overview of use case 1: Laser Plasma Acceleration. The mapping was illustrated using various ontologies.

Planning phase | Sampling phase | Sample preparation | Analysis | Evaluation | Publication

Figure 3: Schematic overview of use 2: Laboratory workflow isotope analysis: Mg isotope analysis of a soil sample. The mapping was illustrated using various ontologies.

6. Concepts and relations

From the use cases described above, we have identified several entities / concepts that are listed in Table 1. Table 1 also includes a brief description and an example for the concepts from the use cases to provide a better understanding of the technical context.

The links between these concepts are given by relations that are listed below Table 1.

The development of the concepts for the single use cases has shown that these concepts are not only applicable to one use case, but can be transferred to all three use cases. This becomes also apparent from the schematic illustrations of the workflows for all use cases. The common concepts are colour-coded in figures 2-4.

Table 1: Concepts identified from use cases.

Concept	Description	Example(s) from use case(s)
Organisation	Institution such as a research institute, company, society, etc.	GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences (GFZ) Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf (HZDR)
Person	Involved people and members of an organization	Bob, Diana & Alice (GFZ use case)
Project	Process that is planned and during which certain tasks are carried out, and has a specific outcome; includes team and starting and end point	Laser Plasma Acceleration (HZDR use case) Mg isotope analysis in a soil sample (GFZ use case)
Experiment/Workflow	Planned scientific procedure for investigating a hypothesis, including the experimental setup (settings, parameters, measurement devices, spatial arrangement of components), selected methods and sequence of processing steps	Use cases in chapter 2, 3 and 4
Processing step	Executed action for further processing of a sample or data for example during an analysis / measurement. Processing steps are combined into a workflow	Sample analysis (GFZ) Optical microscope inspection (HZDR)
Method	Planned defined procedure for an analysis, often associated with a specific scientific instrument, e.g., standard operating procedures (SOPs)	Optical Microscopy (HZDR) Extraction (GFZ)
Device	Scientific instrument for analysing sample properties	Multicollector Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometer (MC-ICP-MS) (GFZ) SEM Microscope (HZDR)
Software	Computer program that accomplishes a specific task	Qtetra (software for element and isotope analysis at GFZ)
Publication	Document describing the results of a research project and published for public access	
Data publication	Release of research data including metadata for instance via data repository	
Software publication	Release of a computer program including documentation for instance via a software repository	
Material	A substance is intentionally used, manipulated, measured, or transformed during an experiment or process. Can be an input or a result/output of a processing step	Input: wafer (HZDR) Output: nano contact platforms (NCP) (HZDR)
Sample / Specimen	Part of a material that has been collected / synthesised for	Plasma (HZDR use I)

Concept	Description	Example(s) from use case(s)
	detailed examination	Soil sample (GFZ) NCP 1 (HZDR use case III)
Aids	Further substances or resources required for processing steps	Acids, solvents, buffer (GFZ) NCP mask (HZDR)
Measured quantity	Physical property or a characteristic of a sample that can be obtained through observation or measurement. It includes a numeric value and a unit	Concentration (GFZ) Weight (GFZ)
Parameter	A device parameter defines a configurable setting or characteristic of a physical or virtual device, controlling its behaviour, data handling, or identification	Extraction time (GFZ) Exposure time (HZDR)
Data	Observations, measurements, files, information, parameter value, etc., obtained during a scientific process, basis for scientific results and their interpretation	Mg isotope ratios (GFZ) SEM image (HZDR) QA report (HZDR)
Data management plan (DMP)	Formal document that describes how data generated during a research project will be handled, stored, and shared	
(Persistent) Identifier	Unique name that identifies a person, an institution, a sample, a publication, an instrument, a method, etc.	e.g., ORCID, ROR, IGSN, DOI, etc.
Material output	Physical result of a processing step	

The interdependence between the concepts can be described by the following relations:

- a *person* is affiliated to an *organisation*
- a *person* can have an *identifier* (e.g., ORCID)
- an *organisation* can have an *identifier* (e.g., ROR)
- a *data management plan* can have an *identifier* (e.g., DOI)
- a *method* can have an *identifier* (controlled vocabulary, ontology)
- a *device* can have an *identifier* (e.g., PIDINST)
- a *publication* can have an *identifier* (e.g., DOI)
- a *software publication* can have an *identifier* (e.g., DOI)
- a *data publication* can have an *identifier* (e.g., DOI)
- a *sample* can have an *identifier* (e.g., IGSN)
- a *person* participates in a *project*
- a *person* has a role in a *project*
- a *project* can have a *data management plan*
- a *project* has one *workflow*
- a *workflow* is composed of *processing steps*
- a *processing step* can have one or multiple *predecessors* and/or *successors*

- a *processing step* has *inputs* (sample, aid or data)
- a *processing step* investigates a *thing* (sample, aid or data)
- a *processing step* has *outputs* (sample, material output, data or publications)
- a *thing* (sample, aid or data) can be derived from another *thing*
- a *processing step* realises a *method*
- a *processing step* can have one or many executing *person(s)* (conductor, executor, agent)
- a *processing step* can have *parameters*
- a *method* can have *parameters*
- a *device* can have *parameters*
- a *processing step* can have *measured quantities*
- a *device* can have *measured quantities*
- a *processing step* can use a *device*
- a *processing step* can use a *software*

7. Terminologies

For a formalized description of these concepts, we applied established general scientific ontologies and domain-specific-ontologies. The criteria are alignment to the FAIR principles and their application in the respective field of research.

On the basis of the concepts, we have identified in chapter 5, we have decided to start with the ontology Metadata4Ing (<http://w3id.org/nfdi4ing/metadata4ing/>). Metadata4Ing is a framework for describing scientific data generation processes, particularly within engineering and related fields. It provides a comprehensive, semantic description covering various aspects from the subject of study and data manipulation (generation, selection, analysis) to details about the data itself, the people and institutions involved (and their roles), and connections to related projects and publications [3]. Metadata4Ing has a relatively low barrier for adoption and is used within the NFDI.

However, as a result of the analysis, it became clear that Metadata4Ing alone is not sufficient to provide a comprehensive semantic description of our use cases. Therefore, we searched for further ontologies which provide the missing concepts.

Metadata4Ing imports various vocabularies and ontologies such as schema.org, DCAT and PROV. Extended ontologies are e.g., ontologies of the OBO Foundry (Open Biological and Biomedical Ontology Foundry). It attempts to use existing OBO terms especially relations where they are relevant [3]. This is a major advantage, as the OBO ontologies are important general scientific ontologies in the life sciences [4]. Additionally, the OBO ontologies are aligned with the well-established upper-level ontology BFO (Basic Formal Ontology) [4]. The OBO Foundry project is a collaborative, open-source effort to create a structured, standardized vocabulary for life sciences. The OBO ontologies are a collection of interoperable ontologies that provide machine-readable definitions of biological entities and their relationships, enabling data sharing, integration, and automated reasoning [5,6].

We also took a closer look at the Helmholtz Digitization Ontology (HDO) ontology developed by HMC. The HDO is developed with the objective of providing harmonized semantics as a reference framework for the Helmholtz digital ecosystem. It follows an established ontology development framework (ODK) and aligns with well-established semantic frameworks, like BFO, in order to increase acceptance towards domain-level re-use and application. One further use case is the semantic representation of FAIR digital objects (FDOs) that will allow data integration between FDOs and the HMC Helmholtz KG [7].

In addition, it is also important to ensure connectivity to the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI). The NFDIcore ontology is designed to formalize and integrate core research data concepts across the NFDI, enabling semantic interoperability, discoverability, and data reuse in research workflows. It provides a machine-readable, structured vocabulary for describing entities like research projects, datasets, research software, data repositories, and related metadata, aligned with FAIR principles and linked to established ontologies [8].

Table 2 shows the detailed mapping of our concepts to the mentioned ontologies: Metadata4Ing, the OBO ontologies, HDO ontology and NFDIcore ontology. For each ontology, the classes are listed with the corresponding IRI in brackets. Sometimes it is not entirely easy to find the suitable concept in an ontology. Therefore, the selected terms may also differ when mapping.

In addition to the concepts, we also took a closer look at the relations (also known as object properties) in the four selected ontologies. The assignment is shown in Table 3. It is notable that the relations between the ontologies exhibit greater interoperability than the concepts.

1. Mapping of concepts and relations

Table 2: Mapping concepts onto ontologies. The concepts described in Table 1 are listed here in the first column (Concept SxL) and are mapped to Metadata4Ing, OBO ontologies, the HDO ontology and the NFDIcore ontology.

Concept SxL	Class in Metadata4Ing	Class in OBO ontologies	Class in HDO ontology	Class in NFDIcore ontology
Organisation	Organization (http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#Organization)	Organization (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_0000245)	Agent (https://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/hob/HDO_00006007)	Organization (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_0000245)
Person	Person (http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#Person)	Person (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/MF_0000016)	Human agent (https://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/hob/HDO_00006023)	Person (https://nfdi.fiz-karlsruhe.de/ontology/NFDI_00000004)
Project	Project (https://schema.org/Project)	Project (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/iao/project)	/	Project (https://nfdi.fiz-karlsruhe.de/ontology/NFDI_00000002)
Experiment/ Workflow	Processing step (http://w3id.org/nfdi4ing/metadata4ing#ProcessingStep) Can have substeps to form workflow.	Experiment (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/AGRO_0000369)	Process (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/BFO_0000015)	data producing process (https://nfdi.fiz-karlsruhe.de/ontology/NFDI_0010029) workflow process (https://nfdi.fiz-karlsruhe.de/ontology/NFDI_0000227)
Processing step	Processing step (http://w3id.org/nfdi4ing/metadata4ing#ProcessingStep)	Material processing (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_0000094)	Measurement process (https://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/hob/HDO_00001070)	/
Method	Method (http://w3id.org/nfdi4ing/metadata4ing#Method)	Method (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/ExO_0000090) Realizable Entity? Information Content Entity?	Technology (https://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/hob/HDO_00001013), Note: This term is broadly defined and also includes methods.	/
Device	Tool (https://nfdi4ing.pages.rwth-aachen.de/metadata4ing/metadata4ing/#Tool)	Device (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/COB_00001300)	For measuring devices: Data source (https://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/hob/HDO_00000004), Note: The term is deliberately broadly defined and also refers to material entities that can be considered data	/

Concept SxL	Class in Metadata4Ing	Class in OBO ontologies	Class in HDO ontology	Class in NFDIcore ontology
			sources. This includes, for instance, measuring devices.	
Software	Tool (https://nfdi4ing.pages.rwth-aachen.de/metadata4ing/metadata4ing/#Tool)	Software (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/IAO_0000010)	Software (https://purl.helmholtz-metadaten.de/hob/HDO_00001023)	Software (https://nfdi.fiz-karlsruhe.de/ontology/NFDI_0000198)
Publication	bibliographic record (http://purl.org/spar/ biro/BibliographicRecord) The actual publication can be easily described by other means.	Publication (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/IAO_0000311)	/	Publication (https://nfdi.fiz-karlsruhe.de/ontology/NFDI_0000190)
Data publication	bibliographic record (http://purl.org/spar/ biro/BibliographicRecord) dataset (http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#Dataset)	Data publication (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/T4FS_0000247)	/	/
Software publication	bibliographic record (http://purl.org/spar/ biro/BibliographicRecord) The actual publication can be easily described by other means.	/	/	/
Material	BFO:continuant (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/BFO_0000002) Implicite by range of "has participant" as base property of e.g., "has input".	Material entity (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/BFO_0000040)	Material entity (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/BFO_0000040)	Material entity (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/BFO_0000040)
Sample (specimen)	BFO:continuant (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/BFO_0000002) Implicite by range of "has participant" as base property of e.g., "has input".	Sample (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/MS_1000457) Specimen (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_0100051) Processed specimen (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_0000953)	/	/
Aids	/	/	/	/
Measured	Quantity kind	Quantity	quantitative data	/

Concept SxL	Class in Metadata4Ing	Class in OBO ontologies	Class in HDO ontology	Class in NFDIcore ontology
quantity	(http://qudt.org/schema/qudt/QuantityKind)	(http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/NCIT_C25256)	(https://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/hob/HDO_00000112)	
Parameter	Has parameter (only available as object property) (http://w3id.org/nfdi4ing/metadata4ing#hasParameter)	Parameter (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/NCIT_C44175)	/	/
Data	Dataset (http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#Dataset)	Data (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/T4FS_0000430)	measurement data (https://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/hob/HDO_00001071)	Experimental dataset (https://nfdi.fiz-karlsruhe.de/ontology/NFDI_0001017)
Data management plan (DMP)	/	Data management plan (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/T4FS_0000196)	data management plan (https://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/hob/HDO_00001035)	/
(Persistent) Identifier	Has identifier (only available as object property) (http://w3id.org/nfdi4ing/metadata4ing#identifier)	Identifier (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/IAO_0020000)	persistent identifier (https://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/hob/HDO_00000043)	Identifier (http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/identifier)
Material output	Has output (only available as object property) (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0002234)	Processed specimen (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_0000953)	Product (https://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/hob/HDO_00001019)	Has output (only available as object property) (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0002234)

Table 3: Mapping of relations onto ontologies. The relations described in chapter 6 are listed here in the first column (Relation SxL) and are mapped to Metadata4Ing, OBO ontologies, the HDO ontology and the NFDIcore ontology.

Relation SxL	Relation in Metadata4Ing	Relation in OBO ontologies	Relation in HDO ontology	Relation in NFDIcore ontology
a person is affiliated to an organisation	Affiliation (https://schema.org/affiliation)	/	/	Affiliation (only available as class) (https://nfdi.fiz-karlsruhe.de/ontology/NFDI_0001102)
a person participates in a project	Participates in (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0000056)	Participates in (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0000056)	Participates in (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0000056)	Participates in (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0000056)
a person has a role in a project	Had role (http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#hadRole)	Has role (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0000087)	Has role (https://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/hob/HDO_00006036)	Has role (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0000087)
a project can have a data management plan	/	Has plan (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/COB_0000084)	/	/
a project has one workflow	Part of (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/BFO_0000050)	/	/	/
a workflow is composed of processing steps	Part of (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/BFO_0000050)	/	/	/
a processing step can have one or multiple predecessors and/or successors	Precedes (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/BFO_0000063)	Precedes (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/BFO_0000063)	/	Precedes (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/BFO_0000063)
a processing step has inputs (sample, aid or data)	Has input (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0002233)	Has input (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0002233)	Has input (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0002233)	Has input (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0002233)
a processing step investigates a thing (sample, aid or data)	Investigates (http://w3id.org/nfdi4ing/metadata4ing#investigates)	Investigates (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/SLSO_0000017)	/	/
a processing step has outputs (sample, material output, data or publications)	Has output (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0002234)	Has output (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0002234)	Has primary output (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0004008)	Has output (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0002234)
a thing (sample, aid or data) can be derived from another thing	/	/	/	/
a processing step realises a method	Realizes (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/BFO_0000055)	Realizes (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/BFO_0000055)	Realizes (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/BFO_0000055)	Realizes (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/BFO_0000055)

Relation SxL	Relation in Metadata4Ing	Relation in OBO ontologies	Relation in HDO ontology	Relation in NFDIcore ontology
a <i>processing step</i> can have one or many executing <i>person(s)</i> (conductor, executor, agent)	Has qualified association (http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#qualifiedAssociation)	/	/	/
a <i>processing step</i> can have <i>parameters</i>	Has parameter (http://w3id.org/nfdi4ing/metadata4ing#hasParameter)	/	/	/
a <i>processing step</i> can have <i>measured quantities</i>	Has assigned parameter set (http://w3id.org/nfdi4ing/metadata4ing#hasAssignedParameterSet) Has output (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0002234)	/	/	/
a <i>method</i> can have <i>parameters</i>	Has parameter (http://w3id.org/nfdi4ing/metadata4ing#hasParameter)	/	/	/
a <i>processing step</i> can use a <i>device</i>	Uses instrument (https://schema.org/instrument)	Uses (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/ECO_9000001)	Uses (https://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/hob/HDO_00006063)	
a <i>processing step</i> can use a <i>software</i>	Uses configuration (http://w3id.org/nfdi4ing/metadata4ing#usesConfiguration)	Uses (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/ECO_9000001)	Uses (https://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/hob/HDO_00006063)	
a <i>device</i> can have <i>parameters</i>	Has parameter (http://w3id.org/nfdi4ing/metadata4ing#hasParameter)	/	/	/
a <i>device</i> can have <i>measured quantities</i>	Has parameter (http://w3id.org/nfdi4ing/metadata4ing#hasParameter)	/	/	/
objects are represented by appropriate identifiers (DOI, ROR, ORCID, IGSN, PIDINST, RAiD, ...)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
objects may have additional identifiers (IRI, string, ...)	Has identifier (http://w3id.org/nfdi4ing/metadata4ing#identifier) Has project ID (http://w3id.org/nfdi4ing/metadata4ing#projectReferenceID) Has ROR ID (http://w3id.org/nfdi4ing/metadata4ing#hasRorId)	Has identifier (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OPMI_0000481)		Identifier (http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/identifier) Note: annotation property

Relation SxL	Relation in Metadata4Ing	Relation in OBO ontologies	Relation in HDO ontology	Relation in NFDIcore ontology
	Has ORCID ID (http://w3id.org/nfdi4ing/metadata4ing#orcidId)			

2. Choice of ontology

Given the mapping options in the previous section no single ontology that can express all the terms could be identified. However, it is possible to select a main ontology to express the structure of all use cases and then to use additional compatible terms from other ontologies to express more fine-grained details.

For this main ontology we select Metadata4Ing. As given in tables 2 and 3 most terms, including all terms that represent the core structure of the use cases, can be expressed using Metadata4Ing. Compared to other considered ontologies, which are all broader in scope, Metadata4Ing is more focussed on the terms needed to express. Additionally, Metadata4Ing includes documented shapes how to use different properties together to express some of the patterns identified for the use cases, such as a documented pattern for connecting processing step, tool and method using Metadata4Ing properties. A particular reason against using multiple OBO ontologies was that this raises many ontological questions whether properties from different ontologies are actually compatible and should be used together which are time-consuming to answer.

The most notable addition from other ontologies is the “wasDerivedFrom” property of PROV (PROV Ontology) [9], which naturally fits into the Metadata4Ing based description, since Metadata4Ing already maps and includes multiple terms to PROV. Additionally, some specific classes from IAO (Information Artifact Ontology), OBI (Ontology for Biomedical Investigations) and CHMO (Chemical Methods Ontology), can be used to provide more specific descriptions (Metadata4Ing is not based on BFO but states to be aligned to BFO [3]). On the other hand, considering relations (=properties) the OBO ontologies use their Relation Ontology (RO) [13] while Metadata4Ing defines its own properties.

Worth to mention is a semantic approach to mapping the Provenance Ontology to Basic Formal Ontology [11]. Other well-known mid-level ontologies based on the BFO are the Common Core Ontology (CCO) [12] (in review as an IEEE standard) or ontologies from the Industrial Ontologies Foundry (IOF) [14]. There are other harmonisation approaches like the EU project OntoCommons across all domains related to materials and manufacturing [15]. But [16] concludes that the harmonisation of DLOs (domain-level ontologies) with TLOs (top-level ontologies) is a crucial step but not enough to establish strong DLO-DLO pipelines.

For practical reasons we stick with Metadata4Ing for the next steps.

3. Handling of fine-grained details

An important part of the semantic description of laboratory processes is the use of the same terms for methods and instruments across experiments. For the detailed description of the experimental methods applied in our use cases we therefore refer to the CHMO which is also part of the OBO foundry [10]. CHMO describes methods and instruments used in chemical experiments, covering data collection, material preparation & separation, and material synthesis. CHMO is designed to work alongside OBI, providing a complementary resource for describing chemical processes.

The use of an ontology such as the CHMO is crucial because it enables a standardized and unambiguous representation of chemical methods and the associated instruments. This is particularly important because different laboratories and researchers may use different terminology, which can lead to confusion and misinterpretation. CHMO creates a common language that improves data interoperability and facilitates the retrieval of information. The use of an ontology also enables automatic conclusions and knowledge discovery as well as simplified data integration and analysis through standardized data annotations.

Table 4 shows examples of the mapping of preparative and analytical methods used in the partner laboratories at GFZ and HZDR to CHMO. Special procedures for preparing rock samples, such as rock crushing, mineral separation or fusion are not included in the ontology and would need to be added.

Table 4: Examples for mapping analytical procedures and analytical methods applied in the GFZ partner laboratories on the Chemical Methods Ontology (CHMO).

Method Name (Partner Laboratories)	CHMO Ontology	Abbreviation
Ball Milling	ball milling (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CHMO_0001654)	
Microwave Digestion	microwave digestion (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CHMO_0001496)	MAD
Leaching	leaching (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CHMO_0001681)	
X-ray Fluorescence Spectroscopy	X-ray emission spectroscopy (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CHMO_0000307)	XRF
Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic Emission Spectrometry	inductively-coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CHMO_0000267)	ICP-AES
Fourier Transform Ion Cyclotron Resonance Mass Spectrometry	Fourier transform ion cyclotron resonance mass spectrometry (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CHMO_0000502)	FT-ICR-MS
Cavity Ring Down Spectroscopy	cavity ring-down spectroscopy (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CHMO_0000450)	CRDS
SEM microscopy	Scanning electron microscopy (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CHMO_0000073)	SEM
UV lithography	ultraviolet lithography (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CHMO_0001417)	

8. Development of knowledge graphs

For each use case we first modelled a pseudo knowledge graph using the identified common concepts and relations described in chapter 6. In the next step we tried to use the M4I ontology to build a knowledge graph adding missing concepts like sample from other ontologies.

For modelling we utilised Protégé and Web Protégé. The resulting knowledge graph files are stored in the project git repository <https://codebase.helmholtz.cloud/semantic-x-lab>

9. Summary and outlook

The decisions taken in this deliverable lay the foundation for further work in the project. In deliverable D1.3, we will update the ontology selection with terms which are needed to include metadata from third-party platforms such as Invenio-based publication platforms or general concepts from Wikidata. In deliverables D2.1 and D2.2, we will reuse the exemplary knowledge graphs created here, and extend them with more similar entities such as laboratories, instruments and methods from local databases, as well as samples, datasets, and publications. This will allow future users to describe new experiments which involve entities from their own work environments.

10. Literature

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